

1 No collisions

The original rule: Avoid collisions with other vehicles, pedestrians and obstacles.

Property specifications:

```
1 nocollision = G( ~NearestNPC(0.1) );
```

2 Finish journey

The original rule: Reach the destination instead of stop half way.

Property specifications:

```
1 finishjourney = G(F[0, 200] (speed > 0.5) | dest(5) );
```

3 Law 38

The original rule: Article 38: Motor vehicle signal lights and non-motor vehicle signal lights indicate: (1) When the green light is on, vehicles are allowed to pass, but turning vehicles shall not hinder the passing of straight vehicles and pedestrians that are being released. (2) When the yellow light is on, vehicles that have crossed the stop line can continue to pass; (3) When the red light is on, vehicles are prohibited from passing. When the red light is on, vehicles turning right can pass without hindering the passage of vehicles or pedestrians.

Property specifications:

```
1 law38_sub1_1 = (trafficLightAhead.color == green) & (stoplineAhead
   (2) | junctionAhead(2)) & ~PriorityNPCAhead & ~
   PriorityPedsAhead;
2 law38_sub1_2 = F[0,100] (speed > 0.5);
3 law38_sub1 = G (law38_sub1_1 -> law38_sub1_2);
4
5 law38_sub2_1 = ((trafficLightAhead.color == yellow) & (
   stoplineAhead(0) & currentLane.number == 0) & (speed > 0.5)) ->
   (F[0,100] (speed > 0.5));
6 law38_sub2_2 = ((trafficLightAhead.color == yellow) & stoplineAhead
   (2)) -> (F[0,100] (speed < 0.5));
7 law38_sub2 = G (law38_sub2_2);
8
9 law38_sub3_1 = ((trafficLightAhead.color == red) & (stoplineAhead
   (2) | junctionAhead(2)) & ~(direction == right)) -> (F[0,100] (
   speed < 0.5));
10 law38_sub3_2 = ((trafficLightAhead.color == red) & (stoplineAhead
   (2) | junctionAhead(2)) & direction == right & ~
   PriorityNPCAhead & ~PriorityPedsAhead) -> (F[0,100] (speed >
   0.5));
11 law38_sub3 = G (law38_sub3_1 & law38_sub3_2);
12
13 law38 = law38_sub1 & law38_sub2 & law38_sub3;
```

4 Law 44

The original rule: Article 44: Where there are two or more motorized lanes in the same direction on the road, the left side is the fast lane and the right side is the slow lane. Motor vehicles traveling in a fast lane shall drive at the speed specified in the fast lane, and those that have not reached the speed specified in the fast lane shall drive in a slow lane. Motorcycles should drive in the rightmost lane. If there are traffic signs indicating the driving speed, drive at the indicated driving speed. When a motor vehicle in a slow lane overtakes the preceding vehicle, it can borrow the fast lane to drive.

Property specifications:

```
1 law44_sub1 = isfastlane;  
2 law44_sub2 = speed >= 20;  
3 law44_sub3 = speed <= speedLimit.upperLimit;  
4 law44_sub4 = F[-6000,6000](law44_sub1 -> law44_sub2);  
5 law44 = G(law44_sub1 -> (law44_sub4 & law44_sub3));
```

5 Law 46

The original rule: Article 46: When a motor vehicle encounters one of the following conditions, the maximum speed shall not exceed 30 kilometers per hour, and the maximum speed of tractors, battery vehicles, and wheeled special machinery vehicles shall not exceed 15 kilometers per hour: (1) When entering or leaving a non-motorized vehicle lane, passing through a railway crossing, a sharp curve, a narrow road, or a narrow bridge; (2) When turning around, turning, or descending steep slopes; (3) In case of fog, rain, snow, sand dust, hail, the visibility is within 50 meters; (4) when driving on icy and muddy roads; (5) When towing a malfunctioning motor vehicle.

Property specifications:

```
1 law_46_sub2 = G( (direction == left | direction == right |  
    isTurningAround) -> (speed <= 30 ));  
2 law_46_sub3 = G( (rain >= 0.5 | fog >= 0.5 | snow >=0.5 |  
    visibility <= 50 ) -> (speed <= 30));  
3 law46 = (law_46_sub2) & (law_46_sub3);
```

6 Law 53

The original rule: Article 53:

- (1) When a motor vehicle encounters a traffic jam at an intersection ahead, it shall stop and wait in turn outside the intersection and shall not enter the intersection.
- (2) When a motor vehicle encounters a motor vehicle in front of the vehicle parked in a queue or is driving slowly, it shall be queued in sequence, and shall not pass through or overtake from both sides of the vehicle in front and shall not park and wait in the area of crosswalks or mesh lines.

- (3) When a motor vehicle is at an intersection or road section with reduced lanes, if there is a motor vehicle in front of the vehicle parked in a queue or driving slowly, one vehicle in each lane shall alternately drive into the intersection or road section with reduced lanes.

Property specifications:

```
1 law53 = G((isTrafficJam & (NPCAhead.speed < 0.5 | NPCAhead(0.5) |  
    junctionAhead(1) ))-> F[0, 200] (speed < 0.5));
```